

Catalog of Perspectives and Concerns

System Objectives:

When evaluating ML solutions, there is a tendency to focus on improving the ML metrics such as the F1-score and accuracy at the expense of ensuring business value and covering business requirements. Success in ML-enabled systems is hard to define with a single metric. One good practice is to define success at different levels.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
Context	the specific circumstances, environment, or conditions in which the ML-enabled system will operate
Need	the requirement, desire, or gap that must be addressed to achieve a particular set of circumstances within a given context
ML functionality	the nature of the learning problem and the desired outcome that the ML model is designed to achieve (e.g., classify customers)
Profit hypothesis	how the ML system's outcomes will translate into tangible gains for the organization
Organizational goals	measurable benefits ML is expected to bring to the organization. <i>E.g.</i> , increase the revenue in X%, increase the number of units sold in Y%, number of trees saved.
System goals	what the system tries to achieve, with the support of an ML model, in terms of behavior or quality.
User goals	what the users want to achieve by using ML. <i>E.g.</i> , for recommendation systems this could involve helping users find content they will enjoy.
Model goals	metrics and acceptable measures the model should achieve (e.g., for classification problems this could involve accuracy > X%, precision > Y%, recall > Z%).
Leading indicators	measures correlating with future success, from the business' perspective. This could include the users' affective states when using the ML-enabled system (e.g., customer sentiment and engagement).
ML trade-off	the balance of customer expectations (e.g., inference time vs accuracy, false positive vs false negative).

User Experience

A good ML-enabled system includes building better experiences of using ML. The goal of this perspective is to present the predictions of the model to users in a way that achieves the system objectives and to gather user feedback to improve the model.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Value</i>	the added value as perceived by users from the predictions
<i>Forcefulness</i>	how strongly the system forces the user to do what the model indicates they should (e.g., automatic or assisted actions).
<i>Frequency</i>	how often the system interacts with users (e.g., interact whenever the user asks for it or whenever the system thinks the user will respond).
<i>Visualization</i>	user-friendly interfaces to showcase the ML model's outputs and facilitate its integration into the customer's existing systems (e.g., specifying dashboard and visualization prototypes for validation)
<i>Learning feedback</i>	what interactions the users will have with the ML-enabled system in order to provide new data for learning, or human-in-the-loop systems where ML models require human interaction
<i>Acceptance</i>	how well and how the model arrives at its decisions
<i>Accountability</i>	who is responsible for unexpected model results
<i>Cost</i>	the user impact of a wrong ML model prediction
<i>User education & Training</i>	the need to provide user education and training on the limitations of the ML-enabled system and how to interpret its outputs

Infrastructure

ML models produced by data scientists typically are turned into functional and connected systems that demand special characteristics when in operation. The goal of this perspective is to cover the execution of the models, the monitoring of both data and model outputs, and its learning from new data.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Data streaming</i>	what data streaming strategy will be used (e.g., real time data transportation or in batches).
<i>Model serving</i>	how the model of the ML-enabled system will be executed and consumed (e.g., client-side, back-end, cloud-based, web service end-point).
<i>Incremental learning</i>	the need for ML-enabled system abilities to continuously learn from new data, extending the existing model's knowledge.
<i>Storage</i>	where the ML artifacts (e.g., models, data, scripts) will be stored.
<i>Monitorability</i>	the need to monitor the data and the outputs of the model to alert/detect when data drifts or changes.
<i>Telemetry</i>	what ML-enabled system data needs to be collected. Telemetry involves collecting data such as clicks on particular buttons and could involve other usage data.
<i>Reproducibility</i>	the need to repeatedly run an algorithm/ML process on certain datasets/experiments and obtain the same (or similar) results.
<i>Maintainability</i>	the need to modify ML-enabled systems to improve performance or adapt to a changed environment.
<i>Integration</i>	the integration that the model will have with the rest of the system functionality (e.g., safety, security, privacy, fairness, legal)
<i>Hybrid decision Intelligence</i>	the essence of combining ML model outputs with rule-based or heuristic decision-making to create a more comprehensive and effective decision intelligence
<i>Cost</i>	the financial cost involved with the infrastructure that could affect architectural decisions. Great models can be unusable due to the cost to run them and maintain them.

Model

Building a model implies not only training an algorithm with data to predict some phenomenon. Several other aspects determine its quality.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
<i>Algorithm & model selection</i>	the set of algorithms that could be used/investigated, based on the ML problem and other concerns to be considered (e.g., constraints regarding explainability or model performance, for instance, can limit the solution options).
<i>Algorithm tuning</i>	the need to choose a set of hyperparameters for a learning algorithm. A hyperparameter is a parameter whose value is used to control the learning.
<i>Input & Output</i>	the expected inputs (features) and outcomes of the model. Of course, the set of meaningful inputs can be refined/improved during pre-processing activities, such as feature selection.
<i>Learning time</i>	the acceptable time to train the model.
<i>Performance metrics</i>	the metrics used to evaluate the model (e.g., precision, recall, F1-score, mean square error) and measurable performance expectations.
<i>Baseline model</i>	the optional simple model that acts as a reference. Its main function is to contextualize the results of trained models.
<i>Inference time</i>	the acceptable time to execute the model and return the predictions.
<i>Model size</i>	the size of the model in terms of storage and its complexity (e.g., for decision trees there might be needs for pruning).
<i>Performance degradation</i>	the awareness of performance degradation. Over time many models' predictive performance decreases as a given model is tested on new datasets within rapidly evolving environments.
<i>Versioning</i>	the versions of libraries, ensuring compatibility, and handling any conflicts or issues that may arise due to dependencies.
<i>Interpretability & Explainability</i>	the need to understand reasons for the model inferences. The model might need to be able to summarize the reasons for its decisions.
<i>Scalability</i>	the need for the model to perform well as the size of the data and the complexity of the problem increases.
<i>Bias & Fairness</i>	the need for the model to treat different groups of people or entities.
<i>Security & Privacy</i>	the need for the model to protect sensitive data and prevents unauthorized access

Data

Poor data will result in inaccurate predictions. Hence, ML requires high-quality input data. Based on the Data Quality model defined in the standard ISO/IEC 25012 and our own experience, we elaborate on the data perspective.

Concern	Addressing this concern involves specifying
Source	from where the data will be obtained.
Timeliness	the time between when data is expected and when it is readily available for use.
Data selection	the process of determining the appropriate data type and suitable samples.
Data dictionary	the collection of the names, definitions, and attributes for data elements.
Quantity	the expected amount of data according to the type of the problem and the complexity of the algorithm.
Accuracy	the need to get correct data.
Completeness	the need to get data containing sufficient observations of all situations where the model will operate.
Credibility	the need to get true data that is believable and understandable by users.
Real usage	the need to get real data representing the real problem.
Bias	the need to get data fair samples and representative distributions.
Consistency	the need to get consistent data in a specific context.
Ethics	the need to get data to prevent adversely impacting society (e.g., listing potential adverse impacts to be avoided).
Anonymization	the need to anonymize or pseudonymize to protect individual identities while still maintaining the utility of the data for ML purposes
Data operations & Modeling	what operations must be applied on the data (e.g., data cleaning and labeling) and what is necessary to convert data in the representation of the model.
Data distribution	the expected data distributions and how data will be split into training, validating and test data.
Golden dataset	the need for a baseline dataset approved by a domain expert that reflects the problem. It is employed to monitor other data acquired afterwards.

How to apply *PerSpecML*

We expect *PerSpecML* to be used by requirements engineers, in collaboration with other stakeholders, to support the specification of ML-enabled systems. The process begins by considering the perspectives. We established an intuitive order to analyze them: system objectives, user experience, infrastructure, model, and data. Given a perspective, a requirement engineer or a stakeholder performing that function can analyze each concern with the recommended stakeholders, also considering the relationships between concerns. If the concern is applicable, it should be specified in the perspective-based ML specification template and classify its relevance into desirable, important or essential.

Perspective-Based ML Task and Concern Diagram

Perspective-based ML Specification Template

Please check our interactive Miro board to access the Perspective-based ML specification template. In addition, you can access the specifications of the *Product classification* Project and the *Market* Project.

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPiQXg7E=?share_link_id=381359836704

Details of the Relationship of Concerns by Perspective

Here, we detail the relationships of each concern considered by *PerSpecML*. These relationships are grouped by perspective but some of them can be related to concerns of other perspectives.

System Objectives Perspective

Relationship		Description
ML functionality	Algorithm and model selection	The ML functionality guides the selection of appropriate ML algorithms. Different tasks (<i>e.g.</i> , classification, regression) require specific algorithms that are suitable for the task at hand
	Data operations and modeling	The selection, transformation and creation of features is influenced by the desired functionality
	Performance metrics	The ML functionality affects how the model's performance is evaluated and measured. The choice of performance metrics depends on the specific task and the priorities of the application. <i>E.g.</i> , in a medical diagnosis task, recall might be more critical to minimize false negatives
	Ethics	The chosen functionality can have ethical implications, especially in sensitive domains. <i>E.g.</i> , ML models for making critical decisions need to be carefully designed to avoid biases and unfair outcomes
Hypothesis	Organizational goals and leading indicators	The profit hypothesis directly aligns the ML system's goals with the broader business objectives. It helps establish specific, measurable targets for generating value, whether it's increased revenue, cost savings, customer retention, or other key performance indicators
ML trade-offs	Performance metrics	The choice of trade-offs can affect the performance of the ML model. <i>E.g.</i> , prioritizing speed over accuracy might lead to the selection of simpler models that can make predictions more quickly but with potentially lower accuracy
	Explainability Interpretability	Trade-offs can affect the interpretability of the ML model. More complex models might offer higher accuracy but be harder to interpret
	Scalability	The trade-offs chosen impact the computational resources. More complex models may require more memory and processing power, affecting the scalability and efficiency of the solution
	Data quality	The trade-offs can impact the volume and quality of data required for training. Some ML models might perform well with smaller datasets, while others might need larger datasets to generalize effectively
	Inference time and model serving	The trade-offs can impact the response time of the system. Choosing trade-offs that prioritize low latency can influence the choice of model architecture and deployment strategy
	Cost	The trade-offs can impact the costs associated with the ML project. More complex models might lead to higher infrastructure costs and operational expenses

User Experience Perspective

Relationship		Description
Acceptance	Performance metrics	The choice of performance metrics allows to ensure that the ML model is being evaluated in a way that is meaningful to the users
	Explainability Interpretability	By emphasizing explainability and interpretability, you cater to stakeholders' desire to comprehend how the model arrives at its decisions, increasing their acceptance and willingness to adopt the model's predictions
	Bias & Fairness	Models that are biased or unfair can have negative impacts on user experience. Defining bias and fairness helps create positive and inclusive user experiences

Infrastructure Perspective

Relationship		Description
Data streaming	Inference time	Data streaming minimizes latency by processing and acting on data in near real time, crucial for time-sensitive applications
	Data operations	data streams may require on-the-fly pre-processing and feature extraction, demanding efficient techniques
	Scalability	Data streaming often involves handling high data volumes. Designing ML systems to handle data streams efficiently requires scalability
	Incremental learning	With data streaming, models can be updated and retrained in real time as new data becomes available, ensuring models remain relevant and accurate
MS	Cost	Different model serving (MS) architectures have different cost implications. Choosing the right architecture can help optimize the infrastructure costs
IL	Acceptance	Incremental learning (IL) may require human oversight to ensure that updates align with performance metrics, business goals and fairness considerations
	High quality data	IL relies on the assumption that new data is of good quality and representative of the problem domain
Storage	Inference time	The choice of storage solutions affects the speed at which data can be retrieved and processed, impacting the overall system's latency and throughput
	Scalability	Scalability is influenced by storage solutions that can accommodate growing data volumes without compromising performance
	Data streaming	Data streaming projects require storage solutions that can handle continuous and high-velocity data influx while maintaining low latency
	Reproducibility	Intermediate storage of cleaned and pre-processed data ensures reproducibility and reduces the need for repeated processing
	Cost	Storage costs can be a significant part of ML project budgets
Monitorability	Performance metrics	Monitorability enables to track the performance metrics of ML models. This helps ensure that ML models are providing accurate predictions over time
	Security Privacy	Keep an eye on any unusual or unauthorized activities related to the ML system's data and models
	High quality data	Tracking the quality of incoming data and identifying potential issues or anomalies is a good practice since poor data might affect the model's performance
Telemetry	Frequency Forcefulness	Capture telemetry data related to user interactions, preferences, and behaviors. This can provide insights into how users are engaging with the ML system
	Learning feedback	Telemetry facilitates a feedback loop by capturing user interactions and responses to model predictions. This feedback can be used to improve model accuracy and relevance

Model Perspective. Part 1

Relationship		Description
Alg. selection	Hyper-parameter tuning	Different algorithms have different parameters that can be set to improve the performance
	Baseline model	When experimenting with multiple ML models comparing against the baseline helps to choose ML models that outperform the initial
	Model size & complexity	More complex ML algorithms might provide higher accuracy but could be harder to interpret, while simpler algorithms are often more interpretable
	Data quantity	Some ML algorithms require larger datasets to perform well, while others can work effectively with smaller amounts of data
Input-Output	Exp & Int	It's easier to interpret models when inputs and outputs have clear meanings
	Data operations	The inputs guide the selection and engineering of relevant features
	Data streaming	The inputs and outputs must be known at hand to set this service
	Model serving	The inputs determine how it will provide data to the model during deployment. The outputs determine how predictions are presented to users
	Incremental learning	The outputs generated by the model can serve as feedback to improve the model's performance
	Hybrid decision Intelligence	The outputs generated by the model can be combined with heuristics to create a more comprehensive solution
HT	Learning time	Longer learning times can provide the opportunity to perform more extensive hyperparameter tuning (HT), leading to better-tailored models
LT	Incremental learning	the learning time (LT) can influence the speed at which ML models iterate and deploy updated versions
	Cost	Longer learning times might require more computational resources, potentially leading to higher costs
PM	Hyper-parameter tuning	Performance metrics (PM) guide model optimization. Adjusting parameters to optimize a specific metric may be necessary
Exp & Int	Bias & Fairness	An emphasis on explainability enables the identification of bias sources within the model
	Maintainability	When a model's outputs are explainable and interpretable, it becomes easier to identify and rectify errors
	Accountability	Defining explainability and interpretability cultivates trust in the model's predictions by making its decision-making process transparent
Scalability	Data quantity & Streaming	Scalability considerations influence how well the model can handle increasing volumes of data, and ensure that the ML model remains effective
	Cost	Scalability involves efficient use of computational resources like memory, processing power, and storage. Properly defined scalability minimizes wastage and ensures optimal resource utilization
	Model serving	Scalability considerations impact how quickly the model can process incoming data and provide predictions within acceptable timeframes
	Learning time	Scalability affects the time it takes to train an ML model
B & F	High quality data	Defining bias and fairness (B&F) guides the data collection process to ensure that representative and unbiased data is used for training the model
	Data operations	B&F considerations influence which features are selected and how they are used to avoid introducing biases in the ML model

Model Perspective. Part 2

S & P	Data selection	Security and privacy (S & P) considerations influence the collection of data, ensuring that sensitive information is not inadvertently included
	Anonymization	Sensitive data may need to be anonymized to protect individual identities while still maintaining the utility of the data
	Model serving	S & P considerations influence how models are deployed and updated, ensuring, <i>e.g.</i> , that endpoints are properly secured against attacks
	Storage	Decisions regarding how and where data is stored are guided by security and privacy concerns to prevent unauthorized access and potential breaches
Inference time	Scalability	Efficient inference times enable the model to handle a larger volume of requests concurrently, ensuring scalability for high user demand
	Data streaming	In scenarios where ML models are integrated into data processing pipelines, fast inference times ensure smooth and timely data flow
	Model serving	For certain deployments, <i>e.g.</i> , on edge devices fast inference times are crucial due to limited computational resources and bandwidth
	Cost	Faster inference times can lead to lower operational costs by reducing the computational resources, especially in cloud-based deployments
MC	Learning and inference time	The time required to train a model depends on the algorithm's complexity or model complexity (MC), and computational demands
PD	Incremental learning	Performance degradation (PD) may signal the need for model adaptation, fine-tuning, or retraining on new data to restore or improve its accuracy
	Versioning	PD insights influence decisions about deploying new model versions to replace outdated ones
V	Model serving	Versioning (V) plays a critical role in managing the release and deployment of models to production environments
	Reproducibility	By documenting each ML model version's configuration and training data, experiments can be reproduced and results can be validated

Data Perspective

Relationship		Description
DD	Performance metrics	Certain metrics, especially in the context of imbalanced datasets, can highlight bias in predictions. Understanding how metrics perform across different data distributions (DD) helps identify potential fairness issues
GD	Performance metrics	A golden dataset (GD) provides a reliable benchmark for evaluating the performance of ML models. It ensures that the model's accuracy, precision, recall, and other metrics are measured against a trusted standard
S	Data streaming	To implement a data streaming project it is necessary to define the data source (S)